

Exploring links: Mapping the needs of the neighborhoods near FATEC Guaratinguetá

Explorando vínculos: Mapeando necessidades dos bairros próximos à FATEC Guaratinguetá

Explorando vínculos: Mapa de las necesidades de los barrios cercanos a FATEC Guaratinguetá

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Abstract: The work proposal is based on mapping the community's needs around FATEC in Guaratinguetá, SP, mediated by research and interaction with curricularization in teaching, research and extension activities. The research method used was a bibliographic review. The study investigated, in an applied nature, exploratory objective, qualitative and quantitative approaches, the historical and legislative evolution of university extension in Brazil. The results showed the active participation of neighboring neighborhoods in this process, highlighting the exchange of knowledge and the practical application of academic knowledge to promote communities' social, cultural and economic development. The Technologist in Commercial Management course is an example of this integration, combining theory and practice to prepare students innovatively and efficiently for the challenges of the commercial sector. The study "Exploring Links: Mapping the Needs of Neighborhoods Close to FATEC Guaratinguetá" illustrated how the university extension identified and met the demands of neighboring communities, contributing not only to the training of students but to the development of areas close to the institution of higher education.

Keywords: *University Extension; Curricularization; Commodification of Education.*

Resumen: La propuesta del trabajo, se basa en el mapa de las necesidades de los barrios cercando la universidad FATEC, en Guaratinguetá, SP, mediada por la pesquisa y interacción con la curricularización de las actividades de ensino, pesquisa y extensión. La metodología de pesquisa se realizó con la revisión de la literatura, el estudio investigado, de carácter aplicado, objetivo y exploratorio, abordajes cualitativa y cuantitativa, la evolución histórica y legislativa de la extensión universitaria del Brasil. Los resultados presentan una participación activa de los

barrios vecinos en este proceso, destacando la troca del saberes y aplicación práctica de lo conocimiento académico para la promoción del desenvolvimiento social, cultural, y económico de las comunidades. Lo curso de Tecnólogo en Gestal Comercial es citado como un ejemplo para esta integración, combinando la teoría y práctica para preparar alumnos de forma innovadora y eficiente para los desafíos del sector comercial. Lo estudio “Explorando vínculos: Mapa de las necesidades de los barrios cercanos a FATEC Guaratinguetá” ilustra como la extensión universitaria a identificar y atender las demandas de las comunidades vecinas, contribuido no solo apenas para la formación de los estudiantes, pero también, para lo desenvolvimiento de las áreas próximas de la institución del encino superior.

Palabras clave: *Extensión Universitaria; Curricularización; Mercantilización de la Educación.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The search for knowledge has always been an intrinsic characteristic of human beings, driving them to explore reality in all its facets and dimensions. This exploration has taken place through different approaches and research methodologies, each with a specific focus and objectives shaped by the nature of the object of study and the researcher's expertise. This diversity of approaches has resulted in a wide range of types of research, each contributing uniquely to the advancement of knowledge in their respective areas. In the context of this study, the literature review research was chosen as the methodology since it allowed the exploration of a problem through theoretical sources already consolidated in previously published articles, books, dissertations and theses. At the same time, the importance of descriptive research was highlighted, especially in the areas of human and social sciences, as it directs its focus to relevant data and questions, providing a deeper and more detailed understanding of the object of study.

Furthermore, the qualitative approach gained relevance by incorporating elements of human subjectivity into the analysis of facts, allowing for a more comprehensive and contextualized understanding of the topic in question. Examining events from philosophical and ideological perspectives enriched the analysis by considering the objective aspects and the nuances and subjective interpretations that permeated the reality studied. Thus, this article's central purpose was to investigate the fundamental role of university extension, highlighting its importance in academic training and the interaction between the university and the community. To this end, a historical and legislative analysis was carried out, seeking to understand the evolution of this concept over time and its impact on contemporary academic practice.

The text explored aspects such as Brazilian legislation related to university extension, the circularization of this activity, the responsibilities of higher education institutions, and the importance of neighboring neighborhoods' active participation in this process. The objective was to provide a comprehensive and critical view of the topic, highlighting challenges, opportunities and perspectives for the future of university extension in the Brazilian context, especially about neighborhoods close to higher education institutions.

University extension was one of Brazil's fundamental pillars of higher education, complementing teaching and research activities. Its primary function was to establish a bridge between the university and society, promoting the exchange of knowledge and the practical application of academic knowledge in favor of communities' social, cultural and economic development. This process was materialized through projects and activities that involved students, teachers and community members, creating an environment of mutual learning and significant social contribution.

University outreach has strengthened ties with local communities at the Faculdade de Tecnologia de Guaratinguetá (Fatec Guaratinguetá). A notable example of this integration was the Commercial Management Technologist course, which aimed to train professionals capable of managing commercial

processes with a practical approach adapted to market needs. This course stood out for its combination of theoretical management knowledge with practical skills, preparing students to face the challenges of the commercial sector innovatively and efficiently.

The study "Exploring Links: Mapping the Needs of Neighborhoods Near Fatec Guaratinguetá" illustrated how university extension could be used to identify and meet the demands of neighboring communities. This scientific initiation report sought to explore how university extension can contribute to and enhance the training of students in the Commercial Management Technologist course and the neighborhoods surrounding the Educational Institution.

2. METHODOLOGY

Human beings' desire and curiosity regarding knowledge lead them to explore reality in various facets and dimensions. Each investigation or approach adopts different levels of depth and specific perspectives according to the object of study, the objectives set and the researcher's expertise. This diversity naturally gives rise to a wide range of types of research.

For this study, we conducted bibliographic review research to explore a problem through theoretical sources in previously published articles, books, dissertations and theses. At the same time, descriptive research is gaining prominence in human and social sciences, focusing on relevant data and questions. In addition, the qualitative approach and analysis incorporate human subjectivity elements by examining facts considering philosophical and ideological perspectives that transcend their essence.

The literature review, in turn, involves conducting bibliographic research to identify, locate, examine, analyze and record the crucial points in the specialized literature related to the delimited issue (Cervo, 2007).

3. DEVELOPMENT

To understand the term and function of university extension, it is necessary to review legislation over time. The first extension actions in Brazil occurred between 1911 and 1917, promoted by the Universidade Passageira de São Paulo, which offered lectures open to the public free of charge (SESU/MEC, 2005). In 1931, the Estatuto das Universidades Brasileiras, enacted by Decree-Law 19.851 of April 11, 1931, defined in Art. 42 that university extension would be carried out through conferences of an educational nature and, in Art. 99, that extension would fundamentally organize university social life (BRASIL, 1931).

In 1961, the first Leis de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação (LDB No. 4,024) mentioned university extension in Art. 69, limiting it to courses and conferences. Decree-Law No. 252/1967, in Art. 10, established that the university should distribute the knowledge produced internally to society. This decree granted autonomy to universities to decide on extension courses and services, using available resources for their development, according to Art. 1 of Decree-Law No.

53 of November 18, 1966. LDB No. 5,540/1968, in Art. 20, reinforced these determinations, stating that it is up to the university to distribute the knowledge produced to the community.

The 1988 Constitution, in Article 207, determined that institutions must comply with the principle of inseparability between teaching, research and extension. LDB No. 9,394/1996, in Article 43, section VI, establishes that higher education aims to address current problems, especially national and regional ones, assist the community with specialized services and create a relationship of reciprocity. Section VII determines that extension must enable the population to share the benefits of cultural creation and scientific and technological research, and extension courses and services, according to Article 44, section IV. Article 77, paragraph 2, mentions that university research and extension activities may receive financial support from the Government, including through scholarships.

The National Congress approved the Plano Nacional de Educação (PNE) by Law No. 10,172/2001, which included goals and objectives for university extension from 2001-2010. Although extension has gained legal notoriety since Law No. 9,394/1996, it is still not fully integrated into the development plans of higher education institutions, especially colleges. Law No. 11,892/2008 assigned extension responsibilities to the Federal Institutes of Education, Science and Technology. Law No. 13,005/2014, which established the PNE 2014-2024, determined that at least 10% of the curricular credits of undergraduate courses be allocated to extension programs and projects, prioritizing areas of great social relevance.

The curricularization of extension, provided for in the PNE, was regulated by Resolution No. 7 MEC/CNE/CES of December 18, 2018. This Resolution establishes that extension activities must comprise at least 10% of the curricular workload of undergraduate courses and be part of the curricular matrix. It also instructs INEP to consider, for the authorization and recognition of courses, compliance with the 10% minimum workload dedicated to extension, the articulation between extension activities, teaching and research, and the qualification of the professors responsible for supervising these activities.

The process of understanding curricularization involves the inseparable principle of teaching, research, and extension, according to art. 207 of the 1988 Constitution determines: "Universities enjoy didactic-scientific, administrative, and financial and asset management autonomy, and shall comply with the principle of inseparability between teaching, research, and extension (our translation)." Only with a flexible curriculum is it possible to meet the requirements of the Plano Nacional de Educação (PNE) for the decade 2014-2024, which provides, in target 12.7: "to ensure at least 10% of the total curricular credits required for graduation in university extension programs and projects (our translation)", a process called curricularization.

Given these circumstances, Gonçalves (2016) reveals the existence of two paths for the institutional process to occur within the academic spectrum: one related to extension activities, which contemplate the principle of inseparability, and the other, as an academic practice focused on philosophical, political and

methodological principles.

There is a risk that certain Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) will create a non-mandatory subject as a complementary activity, which does not contemplate the inseparable principle since this practice already exists. Scholarship students participate in extension activities and receive a certification as a complementary activity (Nogueira, 2000). One way to address this is to create a mandatory subject on extension or a differentiated subject with "special projects," whose objective is to give visibility to university extension, contributing to the student's academic education by inserting the inseparable principle. Outside this standard, there is no curricularization, according to Gonçalves (2016).

Imperatore (2015) emphatically states that it is up to higher education institutions (HEIs) to ensure the academic function of their extension activities, enriching students' training processes. To do so, it will be necessary to overcome obstacles and difficulties, such as "the commodification of education; academicism and authoritarianism of the university, theoretical-conceptual and methodological imprecision, deficient teacher training in Extension, business management of Extension and potential impacts (our translation)" (Imperatore; Pedde, 2015, p.07).

Given this situation, it is clear that there is still a lack of knowledge about the fundamental role of extension in the curriculum of educational institutions, the National Extension Plan and the transformations in the extension concept, which can hinder the curricularization process.

Among managers, the extension concept has not yet been well accepted and understood, and the work is restricted to activities of an assistance nature or simply the provision of services, which presupposes an outdated view of the potential of university extension (Souza, 2019).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 The importance of the participation of neighboring neighborhoods in the curricularization process

The inclusion of university extension as an integral part of the curricular structure of undergraduate courses is legally supported by Article 207 of the 1988 Federal Constitution and Article 43 of the Lei de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação Nacional (LDB) No. 9394/1996. These provisions emphasize the comprehensive education of academics, interaction with the community, and commitment to solving social problems. The enactment of Federal Law No. 13005/2014 made the curricularization of university extension mandatory, directly influencing the recognition of undergraduate courses. This process aims to consolidate the principle of inseparability between teaching, research, and extension, mediated by academic management.

In this context, the participation of neighborhoods adjacent to the university is of utmost importance for the success of extension activities. Such integration allows university extension projects to be contextualized and meet the

community's real needs. Continuous interaction with the local community favors the exchange of knowledge, providing mutual and meaningful learning. Santos (2019) discusses didactic interculturality, highlighting the combination of individual and collective, oral and written processes and the importance of translation work to strengthen social struggles.

Considering the above, the Google Earth tool was used to identify the neighborhoods surrounding Fatec Guaratinguetá. This action was significant for mapping and understanding the demographic and territorial distribution of the neighborhoods, which is essential for formulating extension strategies that genuinely meet local demands.

The Fatec – Guaratinguetá Higher Education Institution is located in a region that borders the Jardim do Sol and Jardim Esperança neighborhoods, Figure 1. Considering the geographic proximity and the potential mutual influence between the institution and these communities, it was decided to develop “probing” studies focused on these neighborhoods. The main objective of these studies is to collect and analyze demographic, socioeconomic and cultural data specific to these areas, Figure 1.

Figure 1: Delimitation of neighborhoods neighboring FATEC – Guaratinguetá, SP.

Source: Google, 2024

When searching for data on the population of these neighborhoods for a survey carried out in 2024, a problem was encountered: the available data referred to the year 2010, which meant a 14-year time lag about the year of the survey.

To resolve this issue, Professor Eduardo helped make an estimate using data from the 2022 census for Guaratinguetá. During this period, a growth rate of 5% was observed, and assuming that this rate applied equally to the neighborhoods near Fatec, the population of these neighborhoods was adjusted according to this growth rate (Figure 2).

The estimated population growth of the city of Guaratinguetá and the two neighborhoods surrounding Fatec, Jardim Esperança and Parque do Sol, between 2010 and 2022.

Figure 2: Estimated growth of neighborhoods neighboring FATEC – Guaratinguetá, SP.

Source: IBGE, 2024

The population growth rate in Guaratinguetá and the neighborhoods of Jardim Esperança and Parque do Sol is relatively low, around 5% over 12 years. This suggests a moderate population expansion, which may be associated with factors such as economic stability, population control policies, or a balanced birth rate.

The relatively uniform population growth between the city and the neighborhoods indicates that urban development may be well distributed. The absence of significant disparities suggests that the neighborhoods surrounding Fatec are following the demographic development of the city as a whole.

4.2 University-community interaction

Population growth that maintains balance facilitates the proximity and integration between Fatec and the surrounding neighborhoods. This allows the university to plan and execute extension projects that truly meet the community's needs without facing the tremendous pressures of overpopulation.

4.3 Social Impact

Although moderate, population growth still poses challenges and social demands that can be addressed through university outreach projects. These projects can target issues such as urban infrastructure, public health, education, and employment opportunities, providing mutual benefits for the university and the community.

That said, the graph indicates moderate and uniform population growth in both the city of Guaratinguetá and the neighborhoods of Jardim Esperança and Parque do Sol. This scenario provides a solid basis for implementing university outreach activities that are effective and aligned with the local community's needs, promoting a beneficial and continuous interaction between the university and the neighboring neighborhoods.

To involve the Commercial Management course in university extension actions aligned with the needs of the local community in Guaratinguetá, especially in the Jardim Esperança and Parque do Sol neighborhoods, here are some suggestions:

Business Training Program: Develop workshops and training courses for local entrepreneurs, covering topics relevant to business management, such as marketing, finance, inventory management and customer service.

Business Consulting: Offer free consulting services to neighborhood small businesses, helping them solve specific problems and develop growth strategies.

Entrepreneurship Fairs and Events: Organize entrepreneurship fairs and events that involve the local community. These events allow students in the course to present projects, products or services and provide networking and business opportunities.

Business Incubator Project: Create a business incubator that offers support and guidance to startups and budding entrepreneurs in the neighborhoods, encouraging innovation and the development of new businesses in the region.

Market Studies and Consumer Research: Conduct market studies and consumer research to understand the needs and preferences of neighborhood residents, helping local businesses adjust their strategies according to the target audience's profile.

Financial Education Program: Promote financial education programs for the local population, including lectures, workshops and informational material on personal financial planning and resource management.

Social Marketing Campaigns: Develop social marketing campaigns in partnership with local companies, focused on social causes relevant to the community, such as sustainability, social inclusion or education.

Partnerships with NGOs and Local Entities: Establish partnerships with non-governmental organizations (NGOs), residents' associations, and other local entities to identify specific community needs and develop joint projects that have a social impact. It is believed that these actions can not only strengthen the bond.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The research conducted in this study highlighted the importance of university extension as a fundamental component of higher education in Brazil, as outlined by a series of legislative and regulatory frameworks. From the first extension initiatives, initiated between 1911 and 1917 by the Universidade Passageira de São Paulo, to the most recent guidelines established by the Plano Nacional de Educação (PNE) 2014-2024, the role of university extension has been continually reinforced and expanded. Legislation, such as the 1931 Decree-Law, the 1988 Constitution, and the various Leis de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação (LDBs), consolidated university extension as an activity inseparable from teaching and research. This inseparability was essential for promoting knowledge that was not only created and transmitted but also applied and disseminated in society. The challenge at the time lay in effectively integrating university extension into higher education courses' curricula, as Resolution No. 7 MEC/CNE/CES of 2018 stipulated.

However, despite regulatory advances, the full implementation of extension

curricularization faced several obstacles. Among these challenges were cultural and institutional resistance within higher education institutions (HEIs), the commercialization of education, and the need for specific training for extension teachers. Overcoming these obstacles required a joint effort by HEIs to create environments conducive to developing extension activities that not only complemented students' academic training but also met social and regional demands.

In this context, it is crucial that HEIs recognize and incorporate extension activities as an integral and mandatory part of the curriculum, avoiding the creation of complementary disciplines that do not reflect the true spirit of university extension.

The participation of neighboring neighborhoods in curricularizing extension is crucial to ensure the contextualization and relevance of extension activities. The identification and demographic analysis of these neighborhoods, as illustrated in the case study of Fatec Guaratinguetá, are fundamental steps for the planning and executing of extension projects that effectively meet local needs. The proposed suggestions for involving the Commercial Management course in extension actions aligned with neighboring neighborhoods present practical and impactful strategies. From business training programs to social marketing campaigns, these actions aim to strengthen the bond between the university and the community and contribute to these areas' economic and social development. Therefore, it is considered that the effective integration of university extension in the curricular structure, combined with the active participation of neighboring neighborhoods, is essential to promote a more contextualized, meaningful education committed to local and social development.

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